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In the collection of materials of the conference, the role and role of Science, Education and production in the era of globalization, the pressing problems of the issues of interaction of these processes, feedback on their solutions were presented by mature specialists of the field.

In addition, research on the scientific and practical topic, carried out in the economics, Exact Sciences, Natural Sciences and socio-humanities during the globalization period, information is presented in the scientific and practical fields, which includes the latest innovative technologies in the fields of production.

It can be argued that this collection is one of the specific intersections of current thoughts and innovative ideas of the world of science. This scientific and practical conference was actively attended by professors and scientific researchers engaged in scientific research in Uzbekistan and foreign countries. In increasing the position of the scientific and practical conference, the professors and teachers of domestic and foreign higher educational institutions made a significant contribution.

Professors and teachers of foreign higher educational institutions who actively participated in the work of the conference made a worthy contribution to the high level of interaction with scientists of our country. The processes of international cooperation with foreign countries and exchange with them in the field of Science in the era of globalization have a positive effect on the development of Higher Education, the fields of Science and production. The materials of this conference are special in that they include a wide range of research, from theoretical developments to practical solutions, demonstrating the diversity of approaches and directions in this area.

In conclusion, it should be noted that this scientific and practical conference will be a very useful collection for everyone who is interested in modern research in the fields of further development of Higher Education, Science, Education and production in the era of globalization. The authors are responsible for the content and quality of the articles and abstracts included in the collection.

PICHIA PASTORIS ZAMBURUG'I YORDAMIDA FARMATSEVTIK OQSILLARNI ISHLAB CHIQRISHNING INNOVATSION USULLARI

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Annotatsiya: Zamonaviy biotexnologiyada rekombinant oqsillar ishlab chiqarish tibbiyot va farmatsevtika sohasining muhim yo'nalishlaridan biri hisoblanadi. *Pichia pastoris* zamburug'i bu jarayonda keng qo'llaniladigan mikroorganizmlardan biri bo'lib, u yuqori mahsuldorlik, tez o'sish va murakkab oqsillarni ishlab chiqarish qobiliyati bilan ajralib turadi. *Pichia pastoris* (hozirgi nomi *Komagataella phaffii*) — metilotrof zamburug' turi bo'lib, u metanolni yagona uglerod va energiya manbai sifatida ishlata oladi. 1960-yillarda kashf etilgan ushbu zamburug' turi rekombinant oqsillarni ishlab chiqarishda keng qo'llaniladi. Ushbu tezis *Pichia pastoris* asosida farmatsevtik oqsillarni ishlab chiqarishning innovatsion usullari ko'rib chiqiladi.[4]

Kalit so'zlar: metilotrofik, *pichia pastoris*, geterologik oqsil, promotor, regulyatsiya, translatsion, sitoxrom.

Pichia pastoris – metilotrofik zamburug' turi bo'lib, boshqa mikroorganizmlarga nisbatan tezroq o'sadi va juda ko'p miqdorda biomassa hosil qilishi, endotoksinlar ishlab chiqarmaydi va ozuqa muhitlari xuddi *Escherichia.coli* kabi arzon. Optimal va yaxshi yo'lga qo'yilgan tizimda rekombinant oqsillarni katta miqdorda ishlab chiqarishga qodir. Ayniqsa, oqsillarni sekretsia qilish qobiliyati yuqori. *Pichia* eukaryotik organizm bo'lgani uchun oqsillarda tabiiy post-translatsion modifikatsiyalarni amalga oshiradi, bu esa oqsillarning faol shakllarini olish imkonini beradi.[5] *Pichia pastoris* zamburug' turlarining barcha qulay belgilariga ega va ko'plab geterologik oqsillarning yuqori titrlarini ishlab chiqarish uchun muvaffaqiyatli ishlatilgan. *Pichia pastoris*dan to'rt marta nakaut hosil qilish yo'li bilan B-bog'langan mannozning kiruvchi qoldiqlari olib tashlandi. Bundan tashqari glikogen ishlab chiqarilgan *pichia pastoris* shtammlari yordamida ishlab chiqarish jarayoni optimallashtirildi. Glikoinjeneriyada *Pichia pastoris*da bir xil yagona glikoform bilan ifodalangan antikor, o'zgaruvchan glikozillanishga ega bo'lgan sut emizuvchilar hujayra kulturasidan olingan glikoform bilan solishtirilganda antikor vositachiligidagi effektor funksiyalarining yaxshilanganligini ko'rsatadi. [1]

Sintetik promotorlar – tabiiy promotorlardan tashqari, ifodani kuchaytiruvchi, qatlamani yaxshilaydigan yoki moslashtirilgan tartibga soluvchi profillarni ko'rsatadigan sintetik promotorlarga qiziqish ortib bormoqda. *Pichia pastoris*dan

22g/l gacha hujayra ichki oqsil va 15g/l gacha ajratilgan oqsil eng ko'p qo'llaniladigan, qattiq nazorat qilinadigan, kuchli va metanol bilan infuksiyalanuvchi AOXI promotorlari olingan. Natijada, bu promotor promotorning kuchayishi va o'zgartirilgan, metonolsiz regulyatsiyasi bilan sintetik variantlarni yaratish uchun turtki bo'ldi. Chunki zaharli va yonuvchan metonoldan foydalanish sanoat jarayonlarida xavfni keltirib chiqarishi mumkin.[2]

Rekombinant o'sish garmoni olish. Rekombinant o'sish garmoni olish uchun *Pichia pastoris* ekspresyon tizimi sifatida boshqa organizmlarga nisbatan juda ko'p afzalliklarga ega. Quyidagi afzalliklari mavjud: oqsillarni qayta ishlash, oqsillarni qatlama va translatsiyadan keyingi modifikatsiyalari shuningdek *Escherichia.coli* bilan taqqoslanadigan oson manipulyatsiya *Pichia pastoris*ning ishchi hujayra banki yordamida hujayra chizig'ini uzluksiz yoki kengaytirilgan kulturada saqlashning barcha xavflari minimallashtiriladi.[4] Erlenmeyer kolbasida o'sadigan *Pichia pastoris* shtammlari o'tkaziladi. Rekombinant inson somotropini GH1 da o'stirilgan geni *Pichia pastoris* kulturasi genomiga AOX1 gen promotori yaqinidagi cheklovdan foydalangan holda kiritiladi. Vektor sifatida pPIC9k plazmidini ishlatiladi. O'zgartirilgan ketma-ketlikka *Sacchoromyces cerevisiae*dan "Prepro-alpha Factor Leader" ketma-ketligi qo'shiladi. Shundan so'ng olingan somotropin kultural muhitga ajralishi mumkin.[3]

Xulosa

Pichia pastoris rekombinant oqsillarni ishlab chiqarish uchun samarali ekspressiya tizimi bo'lib, u farmatsevtik biotexnologiyada keng qo'llaniladi. Tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, ushbu zamburug' inson o'sish garmoni va sitoxrom kabi murakkab oqsillarni ishlab chiqarish uchun mos platforma hisoblanadi. Genetik modifikatsiyalar va fermentatsiya jarayonlarini optimallashtirish orqali ushbu oqsillarning ishlab chiqarish samaradorligini oshirish mumkin. *Pichia pastoris*ning yuqori mahsuldorligi, post-translatsion modifikatsiyalarni qo'llab-quvvatlash qobiliyati va iqtisodiy jihatdan qulayligi uni biofarmatsevtika sohasida muhim vositaga aylantiradi. Ushbu yondashuv inson gormonal terapiyasi va biotibbiyotda qo'llaniladigan oqsillarni ishlab chiqarishni rivojlantirishga xizmat qiladi.

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